

FAIR-IMPACT

Jessica Parland-von Essen[‡], Ingrid Dillo[§][‡] CSC - IT Center for Science, Espoo, Finland[§] DANS Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data, Den Haag, NetherlandsCorresponding author: Jessica Parland-von Essen (parland@csc.fi)

Reviewable

v 1

Received: 10 Oct 2022 | Published: 12 Oct 2022

Citation: Parland-von Essen J, Dillo I (2022) FAIR-IMPACT. Research Ideas and Outcomes 8: e96144.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e96144>

Abstract

In this poster we present the [FAIR-IMPACT project](#), “Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC”, which is funded by the European Commission Horizon Europe programme. The acronym [FAIR](#) stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The project is coordinated by [DANS](#) and supported by 27 additional partners from 11 countries. FAIR-IMPACT will build on the successful practices, policies, tools and technical specifications arising from [FAIRsFAIR](#) other [H2020 projects](#) and initiatives, and from the FAIR and other relevant Working Groups of the former European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC Executive Board](#)). The FAIR-IMPACT project is active between June 2022 and May 2025.

Cascading grants will be available to support uptake of FAIR solutions and practices.

The overall objective of FAIR-IMPACT is to realise a FAIR EOSC, that is an EOSC of FAIR data and services, by supporting the implementation of FAIR-enabling practices across scientific communities and research outputs at a European, national, and international level. Advancing findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability (“FAIRness”) of data and other research objects are at the core of this project, which closely collaborates with the FAIRCORE4ESOC project (<https://faircore4eosc.eu/>).

We will coordinate the implementation of frameworks and the alignment of FAIR data practices on metadata and persistent identifiers (PIDs) in order to achieve the wide uptake of and compliance with FAIR principles by national and European research data and metadata providers and repositories.

In the poster we present our work on the implementation of the FAIR principles and practices. Among other things we aim at a coherent implementation of PIDs and more exact data citation, as services then are able to support better data quality with suitable PID solutions. A broader and more targeted use of PIDs, based on end-user needs, can support trust and risk management and requires collaboration among PID service providers and developing PID policies. Special attention will be paid to reproducibility and to sensitive data. As semantic artefacts are an important element in creating semantic interoperability, they are also regarded as digital objects with their own recommendations for FAIR implementation, as are software. Working together with the FAIRCORE4ESOC project, we can address things like kernel information profiles that are highly relevant for FAIR digital objects.

The project will also focus on increasing data accessibility through enhancing interoperability on all levels, with specific steps taken to address recommendations outlined in the EOSC (The [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#)). Validation of core interoperability components through metadata mechanisms across scientific disciplines, fostering interoperability alignment with the nine European Data Spaces, and the DAMA framework ([DAMA-DMBoK](#)), i.e. the EOSC ecosystem, are of relevance.

Metrics and FAIR assessment are also addressed in this project, that will extend and adapt the FAIRsFAIR data object assessment metrics and [F-UJI tool](#) to be more disciplinary-context aware and to include more discipline specific tests.

The FAIR-IMPACT project will closely work with how the FAIR principles are implemented within the EOSC and how digital objects can be identified and managed.

Presenting author

Ingrid Dillo

Presented at

First International Conference on FAIR Digital Objects, poster

Funding program

European Commission's Horizon Europe funding programme

Grant title

Grant Agreement no. 101057344

Hosting institution

Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)